

On the mean value of the Smarandache LCM function $SL(n)$

Xiaoying Du

Department of Mathematics, Northwest University
Xi'an, Shaanxi, P.R.China

Abstract For any positive integer n , let $SL(n)$ denotes the least positive integer k such that $L(k) \equiv 0 \pmod{n}$, where $L(k)$ denotes the Least Common Multiple of all integers from 1 to k . The main purpose of this paper is to study the properties of the Smarandache LCM function $SL(n)$, and give an asymptotic formula for its mean value.

Keywords Smarandache LCM function, mean value, asymptotic formula.

§1. Introduction

For any positive integer n , we define $SL(n)$ as the least positive integer k such that $L(k) \equiv 0 \pmod{n}$. That is, $SL(n) = \min\{k : n \mid [1, 2, 3, \dots, k]\}$. For example, $SL(1) = 1$, $SL(2) = 2$, $SL(3) = 3$, $SL(4) = 4$, $SL(5) = 5$, $SL(6) = 3$, $SL(7) = 7$, $SL(8) = 4$, \dots , $SL(997) = 997$, $SL(998) = 499$, $SL(999) = 37$, $SL(1000) = 15$, \dots . The arithmetical function $SL(n)$ is called the Smarandache LCM function. About its elementary properties, there are some people studied it, and obtained many interesting results. For example, in reference [1], Murthy showed that if n is a prime, then $SL(n) = S(n) = n$. Simultaneously, he proposed the following problem,

$$SL(n) = S(n), \quad S(n) \neq n? \quad (1)$$

Maohua Le [2] solved this problem completely, and proved that every positive integer n satisfying (1) can be expressed as

$$n = 12 \quad \text{or} \quad n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_r^{\alpha_r} p,$$

where p_1, p_2, \dots, p_r, p are distinct primes, and $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_r$ are positive integers satisfying $p > p_i^{\alpha_i}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, r$.

But about the deeply arithmetical properties of $SL(n)$, it seems that none had studied it before, at least we have not seen such a result at present. It is clear that the value of $SL(n)$ is not regular, but we found that the mean value of $SL(n)$ has good value distribution properties. In this paper, we want to show this point. That is, we shall prove the following conclusion:

Theorem. For any real number $x > 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} SL(n) = Ax^2 + c_1 \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + c_2 \frac{x^2}{\ln^2 x} + \cdots + c_k \frac{x^2}{\ln^k x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where $A = \frac{1}{2} \sum_p \frac{1}{p^2 - 1}$, k is any fixed positive integer, and c_1, c_2, \dots, c_k are calculable constants.

§2. Proof of the theorem

In this section, we shall complete the proof of Theorem. First we need the following two simple lemmas.

Lemma 1. Let $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_t^{\alpha_t}$ be the factorization of n into prime power, then

$$SL(n) = \max(p_1^{\alpha_1}, p_2^{\alpha_2}, \dots, p_t^{\alpha_t}).$$

Proof. This Lemma can be deduce by the definition of $SL(n)$, see reference [1].

Lemma 2. For any arithmetical function $a(n)$, let $A(x) = \sum_{n \leq x} a(n)$, where $A(x) = 0$ if $x < 1$. Assume $f(x)$ has a continuous derivative on the interval $[y, x]$, where $0 < y < x$. Then we have

$$\sum_{y < n \leq x} a(n)f(n) = A(x)f(x) - A(y)f(y) - \int_y^x A(t)f'(t)dt.$$

Proof. This is the famous Abel's identity, its proof see Theorem 4.2 of [2].

Now we complete the proof of our Theorem. We will discuss it in two cases. Let p be the greatest prime divisor of n ,

(a) if $n = p \cdot l$, $p > l$, then use Lemma 1 we obtain $SL(n) = p$.

(b) If $n = p \cdot l$, $p \leq l$, then we will discuss it in three cases.

(i) If n is complete power of prime, that is $n = p^\alpha$, $\alpha \geq 2$, then $SL(n) \leq n$, but the number of this kind n is not exceed \sqrt{n} . Thus $\sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n = p^\alpha \\ \alpha \geq 2}} SL(n) = O\left(x^{\frac{3}{2}}\right)$.

(ii) If n is not complete power of prime, that is $n = l \cdot p^\alpha$, and $l < p^\alpha$, $l \leq \sqrt{n}$, then $SL(n) = p^\alpha$. Thus

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n = l \cdot p^\alpha \\ l < p^\alpha \\ 2 \leq \alpha < \frac{\ln x}{\ln 2}}} SL(n) &= \sum_{2 \leq \alpha < \frac{\ln x}{\ln 2}} \sum_{l \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{p^\alpha \leq \frac{x}{l}} p^\alpha \\ &= \sum_{2 \leq \alpha < \frac{\ln x}{\ln 2}} \sum_{l \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{p \leq \left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}} p^\alpha \\ &= \sum_{2 \leq \alpha < \frac{\ln x}{\ln 2}} \left(\sum_{l \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{\left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}}{\ln \left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}} \cdot \left(\frac{x}{l}\right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha} - \alpha} + O\left(\frac{x^{1 + \frac{1}{\alpha}}}{\ln^2 x}\right) \right) \\ &= \sum_{2 \leq \alpha < \frac{\ln x}{\ln 2}} \left(\sum_{l \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{\alpha x^{\frac{1+\alpha}{\alpha}}}{l^{\frac{1+\alpha}{\alpha}} \ln \frac{x}{l}} + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{1+\alpha}{\alpha}}}{\ln^2 x}\right) \right). \end{aligned}$$

Because $\alpha \geq 2$, so $\frac{\alpha+1}{\alpha} \leq \frac{3}{2}$. We obtain

$$\sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n=l \cdot p^\alpha \\ l < p^\alpha \\ 2 \leq \alpha < \frac{\ln x}{\ln 2}}} SL(n) = O\left(x^{\frac{3}{2}} \ln x\right).$$

(iii) If n is not complete power of prime, that is $n = l \cdot p^\alpha$, and $l > p^\alpha$, $\alpha \geq 1$, $p^\alpha \leq \sqrt{n}$, then $SL(n) = l$. Thus

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n=l \cdot p^\alpha \\ l > p^\alpha \\ 1 \leq \alpha < \frac{\ln x}{\ln 2}}} SL(n) &= \sum_{1 \leq \alpha < \frac{\ln x}{\ln 2}} \sum_{p^\alpha \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{l \leq \frac{x}{p^\alpha}} l \\ &= \sum_{1 \leq \alpha < \frac{\ln x}{\ln 2}} \sum_{p \leq x^{\frac{1}{2\alpha}}} \left(\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{x}{p^\alpha} \right)^2 + O\left(\frac{x}{p^\alpha} \right) \right) \\ &= \sum_{1 \leq \alpha < \frac{\ln x}{\ln 2}} \left(\frac{x^2}{2} \sum_{p \leq x^{\frac{1}{2\alpha}}} \frac{1}{p^{2\alpha}} + O\left(\sum_{p \leq x^{\frac{1}{2\alpha}}} \frac{x}{p^\alpha} \right) \right), \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{x^2}{2} \sum_{1 \leq \alpha < \frac{\ln x}{\ln 2}} \sum_{p \leq x^{\frac{1}{2\alpha}}} \frac{1}{p^{2\alpha}} &= \frac{x^2}{2} \sum_{1 \leq \alpha < \frac{\ln x}{\ln 2}} \left(\sum_p \frac{1}{p^{2\alpha}} - \sum_{p > x^{\frac{1}{2\alpha}}} \frac{1}{p^{2\alpha}} \right) \\ &= \frac{x^2}{2} \sum_p \frac{1}{p^2} \frac{1 - \frac{1}{p^{2\lfloor \frac{\ln x}{\ln 2} \rfloor}}}{1 - \frac{1}{p^2}} - \frac{x^2}{2} \sum_{1 \leq \alpha < \frac{\ln x}{\ln 2}} \sum_{p > x^{\frac{1}{2\alpha}}} \frac{1}{p^{2\alpha}} \\ &= \frac{x^2}{2} \sum_p \frac{1}{p^2 - 1} + O\left(\sum_{1 \leq \alpha < \frac{\ln x}{\ln 2}} x^2 \cdot x^{-\frac{2\alpha-1}{2\alpha}} \right) \\ &= 7Ax^2 + O\left(\sum_{1 \leq \alpha < \frac{\ln x}{\ln 2}} x^{\frac{2\alpha+1}{2\alpha}} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Using the same method, we deduce that

$$O\left(\sum_{1 \leq \alpha < \frac{\ln x}{\ln 2}} \sum_{p \leq x^{\frac{1}{2\alpha}}} \frac{x}{p^\alpha} \right) = O(x).$$

Because $\alpha \geq 1$, so $\frac{2\alpha+1}{2\alpha} \leq \frac{3}{2}$. Thus

$$\sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n=l \cdot p^\alpha \\ l > p^\alpha \\ 1 \leq \alpha < \frac{\ln x}{\ln 2}}} SL(n) = Ax^2 + O\left(\sum_{1 \leq \alpha < \frac{\ln x}{\ln 2}} x^{\frac{3}{2}} \right) = Ax^2 + O\left(x^{\frac{3}{2}} \ln x\right),$$

where $A = \frac{1}{2} \sum_p \frac{1}{p^2 - 1}$.

Combining the above two cases, we may immediately get following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} SL(n) &= \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ p > l \\ p > \sqrt{n}}} p + \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ p \leq l}} SL(n) \\ &= \sum_{l \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{l < p \leq \frac{x}{l}} p + Ax^2 + O\left(x^{\frac{3}{2}} \ln x\right). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Let $a(n)$ denote the characteristic function of the prime. That is,

$$a(n) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } n \text{ is prime;} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Then we have $A(x) = \sum_{1 < n \leq x} a(n) = \sum_{p \leq x} 1 = \pi(x)$.

Thus by Lemma 2

$$\sum_{l < p \leq \frac{x}{l}} p = \sum_{l < n \leq \frac{x}{l}} a(n)n = \pi\left(\frac{x}{l}\right) \frac{x}{l} + \pi(l)l - \int_l^{\frac{x}{l}} \pi(t)dt,$$

where $\pi(x) = \frac{x}{\ln x} + A_1 \frac{x}{\ln^2 x} + A_2 \frac{x}{\ln^3 x} + \dots + A_n \frac{x}{\ln^n x} + O\left(\frac{x}{\ln^{n+1} x}\right)$, A_i are calculable constants, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

Then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{l \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{l < p \leq \frac{x}{l}} p &= \sum_{l \leq \sqrt{x}} \left(\pi\left(\frac{x}{l}\right) \frac{x}{l} + \pi(l)l - \int_l^{\frac{x}{l}} \pi(t)dt \right) \\ &= \sum_{l \leq \sqrt{x}} \left(\frac{x^2}{l^2 \ln \frac{x}{l}} + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{A_i x^2}{l^2 \ln^i \frac{x}{l}} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{n+1} \frac{x}{l}}\right) - \int_l^{\frac{x}{l}} \pi(t)dt \right), \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where

$$\int_l^{\frac{x}{l}} \pi(t)dt = \int_l^{\frac{x}{l}} \frac{t}{\ln t} dt + \sum_{i=1}^n \int_l^{\frac{x}{l}} \frac{A_i t}{\ln^{i+1} t} dt + O\left(\int_l^{\frac{x}{l}} \frac{t}{\ln^{n+1} t} dt\right).$$

Integration by parts give us

$$\int_l^{\frac{x}{l}} \frac{t}{\ln t} dt = \frac{x^2}{2l^2 \ln \frac{x}{l}} + \frac{x^2}{4l^2 \ln^2 \frac{x}{l}} + \frac{x^2}{4l^2 \ln^3 \frac{x}{l}} + \dots + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{n+1} \frac{x}{l}}\right),$$

$$\int_l^{\frac{x}{l}} \frac{t}{\ln^2 t} dt = \frac{x^2}{2l^2 \ln^2 \frac{x}{l}} + \frac{x^2}{2l^2 \ln^3 \frac{x}{l}} + \frac{3x^2}{4l^2 \ln^4 \frac{x}{l}} + \dots + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{n+1} \frac{x}{l}}\right),$$

...

$$\int_l^{\frac{x}{l}} \frac{t}{\ln^n t} dt = \frac{x^2}{2l^2 \ln^n \frac{x}{l}} + \frac{nx^2}{4l^2 \ln^{n+1} \frac{x}{l}} + \frac{n(n+1)x^2}{8l^2 \ln^{n+2} \frac{x}{l}} + \dots + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{n+1} \frac{x}{l}}\right).$$

Combining above formulas, and take them in (3), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{l \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{l < p \leq \frac{x}{l}} p &= \sum_{l \leq \sqrt{x}} \left(B_1 \frac{x^2}{l^2 \ln \frac{x}{l}} + B_2 \frac{x^2}{l^2 \ln^2 \frac{x}{l}} + \dots + B_n \frac{x^2}{l^2 \ln^n \frac{x}{l}} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{n+1} x}\right) \right) \quad (4) \\
 &= \sum_{l \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{x^2}{l^2} \left[\frac{B_1}{\ln x} \left(\frac{1}{1 - \frac{\ln l}{\ln x}} \right) + \frac{B_2}{\ln^2 x} \left(\frac{1}{1 - \frac{\ln l}{\ln x}} \right)^2 + \dots + \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \frac{B_n}{\ln^n x} \left(\frac{1}{1 - \frac{\ln l}{\ln x}} \right)^n + O\left(\frac{1}{\ln^{n+1} x} \left(\frac{1}{1 - \frac{\ln l}{\ln x}} \right)^{n+1} \right) \right] \\
 &= \sum_{l \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{x^2}{l^2} \left[B_1 \left(\frac{1}{\ln x} + \frac{\ln l}{\ln^2 x} + \frac{\ln^2 l}{\ln^3 x} + \dots + O\left(\frac{1}{\ln^n x}\right) \right) \right. \\
 &\quad + B_2 \left(\frac{1}{\ln x} + \frac{\ln l}{\ln^2 x} + \frac{\ln^2 l}{\ln^3 x} + \dots + O\left(\frac{1}{\ln^n x}\right) \right)^2 \\
 &\quad + B_3 \left(\frac{1}{\ln x} + \frac{\ln l}{\ln^2 x} + \frac{\ln^2 l}{\ln^3 x} + \dots + O\left(\frac{1}{\ln^n x}\right) \right)^3 + \dots + \\
 &\quad \left. B_k \left(\frac{1}{\ln x} + \frac{\ln l}{\ln^2 x} + \frac{\ln^2 l}{\ln^3 x} + \dots + O\left(\frac{1}{\ln^n x}\right) \right)^k + O\left(\frac{1}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right) \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

where B_i are constants, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

We know that $\sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{\ln^k l}{l^2} = c$, thus

$$\sum_{l \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{\ln^k l}{l^2} = \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{\ln^k l}{l^2} - \sum_{l > \sqrt{x}} \frac{\ln^k l}{l^2} = c - O\left(\frac{\ln^k x}{\sqrt{x}}\right).$$

In (4) every coefficient of $\frac{x^2}{\ln^k x}$ is calculable, where k is any fixed positive integer.

So we obtain that

$$\sum_{l \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{l < p \leq \frac{x}{l}} p = c_1 \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + c_2 \frac{x^2}{\ln^2 x} + \dots + c_k \frac{x^2}{\ln^k x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right).$$

Combining this formula with (2), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{n \leq x} SL(n) &= \sum_{l \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{l < p \leq \frac{x}{l}} p + Ax^2 + O\left(x^{\frac{3}{2}} \ln x\right) \\
 &= Ax^2 + c_1 \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + c_2 \frac{x^2}{\ln^2 x} + \dots + c_k \frac{x^2}{\ln^k x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),
 \end{aligned}$$

where $A = \frac{1}{2} \sum_p \frac{1}{p^2 - 1}$, k is any fixed positive integer, and c_1, c_2, \dots, c_k are calculable constants.

This completes the proof of the theorem.

References

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